

Abdul Syahid <abdul.syahid@iain-palangkaraya.ac.id>

MS #7911: Submission received for Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)

1 pesan

Administrators of Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) <editors-libphilprac-7911@dcunl.bepress.com>

20 Mei 2020
17.31

Kepada: =?UTF-8?Q?=22Abdul_Syahid=22?= <abdul.syahid@iain-palangkaraya.ac.id>

Cc: The Authors <authors-libphilprac-7911@dcunl.bepress.com>, The Administrators <editors-libphilprac-7911@dcunl.bepress.com>

A new submission for Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal) has been uploaded by "Abdul Syahid" <abdul.syahid@iain-palangkaraya.ac.id>.

The authors are:

"Abdul Syahid" <abdul.syahid@iain-palangkaraya.ac.id>

The title is:

"E-Learning Research in Asia during 1996-2018 and the Four Country Indicators"

The keywords are:

e-learning, research, Asia, metrics, country indicators

The disciplines are:

Library and Information Science | Online and Distance Education

The submission has been assigned #7911. Please refer to this number in any correspondence related to the submission.

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Abdul Syahid <abdul.syahid@iain-palangkaraya.ac.id>

MS #7911: PDF file created for "E-Learning Research in Asia during 1996-2018 and the Four Country Indicators"

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MS #7911 - Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)

2 pesan

Mary Bolin <editor-libphilprac-7911-2370615@dcunl.bepress.com>

8 September 2020 19.58

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Dear Abdul Syahid,

Congratulations! We are pleased to inform you that your article has been favorably reviewed and will appear in Library Philosophy and Practice. LPP has a cumulative yearly volume. Your article will be published immediately

Thanks for your interest in LPP.

Sincerely,
Mary Bolin

Mary K. Bolin, PhD
Professor Emeritus
University of Nebraska-Lincoln Libraries
Lincoln NE 68588-4100
mbolin2@unl.edu

Abdul Syahid <abdul.syahid@iain-palangkaraya.ac.id>

8 September 2020 20.50

Kepada: Mary Bolin <editor-libphilprac-7911-2370615@dcunl.bepress.com>

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Thank you so much for the great news!

[Kutipan teks disembunyikan]

Abdul Syahid <abdul.syahid@iain-palangkaraya.ac.id>

MS #7911: New submission posted to Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)

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Dear Abdul Syahid,

Your submission "E-Learning Research in Asia during 1996-2018 and the Four Country Indicators" (MS #7911) has been posted to Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal).

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